

Synthesis of some potential antibacterial pyrazoles and pyrazolones

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1-Guanyl-3-methyl-4-[4'-(substituted)sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one nitrate and 1-guanyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-[4'-(substituted)-sulphonamoyl]azopyrazole nitrate have been synthesised and characterised by spectral techniques.

Pyrazole nucleus and pyrazolones are associated with broad spectrum of biological activities¹. Sulphonamides are drugs of proven therapeutic importance². In view of biological and medicinal activities³ displayed by these heterocycles and sulphonamides, various pyrazole and pyrazolone derivatives of sulphonamides have been synthesised by reaction of aminoguanidine nitrate with products obtained from the reaction between diazonium salts and active methylene compounds.

Treatment of ethylacetoacetate and dibenzoylmethane with different diazonium salts in presence of sodium acetate gave 1-ethyl-2-[4'-(substituted)sulphonamoyl]-hydrazono-1,3-dioxobutyrate and 1,3-diphenyl-2-[4'-(substituted)sulphonamoyl]hydrazonopropane-1,3-diones, which on reaction with aminoguanidine nitrate in glacial acetic acid medium resulted in the formation of 1-guanyl-3-methyl-4-[4'-(substituted)sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one nitrate (1) and 1-guanyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-[4'-(substituted)sulphonamoyl]azopyrazole nitrate (2) respectively (Scheme 1).

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 833 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Shimadzu 160A spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian instrument (270 Hz) using TMS as internal standard.

1-Guanyl-3-methyl-4-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)-sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one nitrate (1) : The sulphonamide (0.01 mol) dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° was added to a cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g) in portions. The diazonium salt so formed was filtered into already cooled (0°) solution mixture of sodium acetate (8 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), and the mixture was stirred vigorously. The resulting brown solid was washed with water and crystallized from ethanol, (75%), m.p. 166–168° (Found : C, 67.36; H,

Scheme 1

6.62; N, 21.58. C₁₈H₂₂O₅N₅S calcd. for : C, 67.68; H, 6.94; N, 21.92%; λ_{max} 349.0, 246.0 nm; ν_{max} 3400 (NH), 1600 (CO), 1680 (C=N or C=C), 1520 (NH-N=C), 1130 cm⁻¹ (SO₂); δ (DMSO-d₆/TMS) 2.55 (3H, s, COCH₃), 1.35 (3H, t, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.30 (2H, q, COOCH₂), 14.70 (1H, NH hydrogen-bonded), 7.20–8.10 (4H, q, substituted-phenyl). Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared by coupling appropriate sulphonamides with ethylacetoacetate.

To 1-ethyl-2-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-1,3-ketobutyrate (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (10–15 ml), a solution of aminoguanidine nitrate

Note

(0.001 mol) in acetic acid (5 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol to give 1-guanyl-3-methyl-4-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one nitrate (55%), m.p. 265–267° (Found : C, 40.55; H, 4.01, N, 28.40. $C_{17}H_{21}O_6N_{10}S$ calcd. for : C, 41.55; H, 4.10; N, 28.44%); λ_{\max} 350, 252, 217 nm; ν_{\max} 3400 (NH), 1600 (CO), 1510 (NH–N=C), 1130 (SO₂), 820 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); δ 2.30 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.0–8.0 (4H, q, substituted-phenyl), 8.2 (2H, s, NH₂), 12.8 (1H, NH hydrogen-bonded). Similarly, other derivatives were obtained (yields 50–60%) : **1b**, m.p. 265–267°, **c**, 195–197°, **d**, 260–261°; **e**, 265–268°; **f**, 240–242°; **g**, 255–258°.

1-Guanyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)sulphonamoyl]azopyrazole nitrate (2) : The starting material 1,3-diphenyl-2-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-1,3-dione was prepared by the method similar to 1-ethyl-2-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-1,3-dioxobutyrate except that 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione was taken in place of ethyl acetoacetate for coupling the diazonium salt of sulphadiazine. The colour of the synthesised compound (75%) was yellow, m.p. 183–184° (Found : C, 63.36; N, 13.39; H, 4.42. $C_{27}H_{23}O_5N_4S$ calcd. for : C, 63.08; N, 13.62; H, 4.51%); λ_{\max} 366, 252, 216 nm; ν_{\max} 3400 (NH), 1600 (CO), 1130 (SO₂), 1510 (NH–N=C) and 750 cm⁻¹ (substituted-phenyl); δ 2.3 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.0–8.0 (14H, m, ArH), 13.2 (1H, NH hydrogen-bonded). Similarly other compounds were prepared.

To 1,3-diphenyl-2-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)sulphonamoyl]hydrazono-1,3-dione (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (10–15 ml), a solution of aminoguanidine nitrate (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (10–15 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 1-guanyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-[4'-(4'',6''-dimethylpyrimidinyl)sulphonamoyl]azopyrazole nitrate (60%) m.p. 150–152° (Found : C, 54.95; N, 22.52; H, 4.54. $C_{28}H_{27}O_5N_{10}S$ calcd. for : C, 54.67; N, 22.77; H, 4.42%); λ_{\max} 347, 252, 217 nm; ν_{\max} 3400–3210 (NH-doublet), 1600 (C=C or C=N), 1510 (N=N), 1125 (SO₂), 720 cm⁻¹ (substituted-phenyl); δ 2.3 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.0–8.0 (14H, m, substituted phenyl), 8.2 (2H, s, NH₂). Similarly other substituted azopyrazoles were prepared (yields 40–60%) : **2b**, m.p. 140–142°, **c**, 110–113°; **d**, 108–109°; **e**, 150–152°; **f**, 110–111°; **g**, 105–108°.

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